

DAMAGE PREDICTION IN QUASI-STATICALLY INDENTED SANDWICH COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING A TWO-REGION PLATE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

A model is developed for predicting indentation depth, diameter and planar delamination area for thin face sheet, honeycomb core sandwich composites subject to quasi-static indentation loading. The model is primarily based on the Ritz method of energy minimization and is restricted to thin face sheet composites where the deformation is reasonably localized. The assumed displacement function contains unknown parameters defining the peak face sheet displacement and the indentation diameter. Nonlinear plate theory is utilized, and energy contributions from face sheet bending and membrane stresses are therefore accounted for, as are the contributions from both elastic and inelastic core deformations during loading and unloading. Further, the face sheet is divided into two regions, an inner region that is delaminated and an outer region that is intact, and the radius of the boundary between them represents a third unknown parameter that is evaluated during the Ritz minimization. Model predictions are validated by comparison with experimental results for four different quasi-static indentation geometries, all of which consider sandwich plates with eight ply carbon/epoxy, quasi-isotropic face sheets and aluminum honeycomb cores. Geometrical variations are obtained by varying the core density, thickness and indenter diameter. It is shown that the model closely recreates the experimentally observed load versus displacement response and residual dent depth. Residual dent diameter and delamination diameter are generally slightly over-predicted.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composites are stiff, lightweight structures that offer high resistance to bending and in-plane compressive loads. These structures are useful in aviation, space and naval applications. However, when in use as structural components, low-velocity impact (LVI) by external sources such as flying debris, hail or bird strikes can cause internal damage in the form of face sheet debonding, matrix cracking, delaminations and core crushing [1-4]. Such damage can significantly reduce the strength, stiffness and/or life of the structure [5,6]. The ability to predict and design against such deleterious effects is therefore of significant practical importance.

A number of approaches exist in the literature for modeling the response of sandwich structures to LVI [7-20]. Among others, these include spring-mass-damper models [7-9], closed-form engineering mechanics models [12, 16, 17], energy-based analytical models [10, 11, 18], and finite element models [13, 14, 17, 19, 20]. However, these models have their limitations in either correctly implementing the face sheet and core damage onset and progression, correctly representing the indenter to face sheet contact region, and accurate through-thickness damage representation within the face sheet. In order to provide a simple yet accurate design tool, a model was recently developed [18] that uses both engineering mechanics and the Ritz method of energy minimization to model the loading and unloading response of honeycomb core sandwich structures under quasi-static indentation (QSI) loading. QSI loading was chosen as it has been shown that the nature and extent of damage is essentially the same

between QSI and LVI [21, 22]. The model of Ref. [18] predicts the external dent radius and dent depth up to the barely visible damage threshold. However, the model requires a user-assumed ratio of the delamination to dent radius in order to account for the reduced stiffness within the damaged region of the face sheet. This represents a clear limitation to the model's true predictive ability, as it either imparts uncertainty, as in the case of a true assumption, or necessitates a certain level of experimental results to justify the choice of a specific ratio for the geometry that is being considered. Also, the predicted load versus displacement response subsequent to delamination onset is not entirely consistent with what has been observed experimentally. Specifically, compared to experiments, the model predicts too little softening in the local response immediately following core crushing and insufficient stiffening at elevated load [18].

In the current work, the model of Ref. [18] is improved to address the above shortcomings. The initial regime, prior to core crushing, utilizes an existing engineering mechanics approach [12,16,18]. For the remainder of the loading and unloading process, the Ritz method of energy minimization is used. A deflection function containing unknown parameters defining the maximum face sheet displacement and the indentation diameter is assumed. Further, the face sheet is divided into two regions, an inner region that is damaged by matrix cracking and delamination and an outer region that is intact, and the radius of the boundary between these regions represents a third unknown parameter that is evaluated during the Ritz minimization. For this reason, the approach is referred to as a two-region plate model. Thus, the current model directly evaluates the percentage of the indented region that is damaged, and therefore the ratio of the delamination to dent radius, whereas in [18] this was assumed a priori. As in Ref. [18], an equivalent flat-nosed indenter assumption is used. This assumption, coupled with the low stiffness of the inner, damaged region, causes the face sheet deformations to be relatively localized, and for this reason the current model is restricted to sandwich composites with relatively thin face sheets.

2 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1 presents the geometry that is considered [18]. The lower face sheet of the sandwich structure is supported on a rigid substrate while the top face sheet is quasi-statically indented. A schematic of the load-displacement response identifying the different loading regimes is presented in Figure 2. The model considers damage created using a spherical indenter and is valid up to the barely visible external damage threshold. Unlike the earlier model by Singh et al. [18] that was divided into four regimes, the present model is divided into three regimes. This is because the present model assumes face sheet damage, i.e., matrix cracking and delaminations, occur simultaneously with core crushing. This simplifies the model to a great extent, doing away with some of the assumptions in the earlier model, especially with regards to prediction of the delamination onset load. In the present model, Regime I represents the initial elastic response which ends at the assumed simultaneous onset of core and face sheet damage, Regime II represents the region between the core and face sheet damage onset load to the peak load, and Regime III represents unloading. The procedure for modeling each of the three regimes is described in what follows, with the two-region plate model being introduced in Regime II.

Figure 1: Geometry considered.

Figure 2: Representation of sandwich loading-unloading response showing different modeling regimes.

2.1 Regime I: Low load elastic regime

Regime I begins at zero load and ends at the core crush onset load. This regime is modeled identically to that described in Singh et al. [18] and utilizes a combination of local Hertzian indentation of an elastic half-space and small deflection plate theory for a circular isotropic plate on an elastic foundation [12,18, 23].

2.2 Regime II: Core crush onset load to peak load

Regime II begins at the onset of core crushing which is the end of Regime I. To simplify analysis the model assumes that matrix cracking and delaminations occur simultaneously with core crushing. A two-region plate model based on the Ritz method of energy minimization is used in this regime. The fundamental idea behind the two-region plate model is presented schematically in Figure 3. In this figure, b represents the indenter-face sheet contact radius, c represents the planar delamination radius and a represents the external dent radius. The planar delamination radius depicts an equivalent circular approximation of the total delaminated area of the face sheet. While b is assumed constant with increasing load P , c and a grow simultaneously with increasing maximum face sheet displacement w_o . The values of c , a and w_o are solved for in the manner described in what follows.

Figure 3: Boundaries within the two-region plate model.

The displacement field chosen in Ref. [18] is also used in the present work and is given by

$$w = \begin{cases} w_o \left[1 - 3 \left(\frac{r-b}{a-b} \right)^2 + 2 \left(\frac{r-b}{a-b} \right)^3 \right] & \text{for } b \leq r \leq a \\ w_o & \text{for } r \leq b \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The choice of displacement field is a compromise between complexity to capture the desired behavior and simplicity to readily yield an analytical solution. To this end, Eq. (1) assumes an equivalent flat-nosed indenter within the Hertzian contact radius ($r \leq b$), enforces zero slope conditions at the indenter-to-face sheet contact periphery ($r = b$) and at the outer edge of the dented region ($r = a$), and ensures that the displacement at $r = a$ equals zero. Note that c does not factor directly into the displacement equation and a continuous displacement field through a single function is maintained from b to a .

The face sheet deformation behavior with increasing load consists of both bending and membrane effects. The total potential energy, Π , of the deformed plate is evaluated as [24]

$$\Pi = U_b + U_m - V \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2) U_b is the bending strain energy of the face sheet, U_m is the membrane strain energy and V is the total work done. Using the standard expressions for U_b and U_m for an axisymmetric circular plate [24] results in piecewise integrals for each term over the damaged ($b \leq r \leq c$) and undamaged ($c \leq r \leq a$) regions of the plate as

$$U_b = \pi D_{res} \int_b^c \left[r \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2 + 2\nu_{res} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right) \right] dr \quad (3)$$

$$+ \pi D_r \int_c^a \left[r \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2 + 2\nu_r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right) \right] dr$$

$$U_m = \frac{\pi h_f}{4} \left(\frac{E_{res}}{(1-\nu_{res}^2)} \int_b^c r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^4 dr + \frac{E_r}{(1-\nu_r^2)} \int_c^a r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^4 dr \right) \quad (4)$$

where D_r is the isotropic radial bending stiffness, and E_r and ν_r are the effective, isotropic, radial Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. For quasi-isotropic laminates, these latter two quantities may be evaluated using classical laminated plate theory, as the in-plane modulus and Poisson's ratio will be independent of direction. When D_r , E_r and ν_r are used with the subscript "res," they refer to the "residual properties," i.e., as evaluated in the damaged portion of the face sheet. These properties (D_{res} , E_{res} and ν_{res}) are computed by the method described in Ref. [18], which assumes that all interfaces except the top-most and the midplane are delaminated and that matrix crack saturation spacing [25] has been reached in all plies within the delaminated portion of the plate. These assumptions are consistent with experimental observations [1-6], except that the experimentally observed delaminations are not each circular and of outer radius c , and the damaged region does not necessarily exhibit fully saturated matrix cracking. Rather, the observed delaminations fall into quadrants roughly following the back surface ply angle, are oblong, and have a major axis length that increases with increasing distance from the indented surface. Matrix cracks are primarily observed where the delaminations change plane. Thus, the predicted values of D_{res} and E_{res} would be expected to be lower than those observed in practice.

The total work done, V , considers that done by the applied load, P , and the core resistive pressure, p_{oc} . This work done by the core resistive pressure is evaluated by subdividing the contributions from the region beneath the indenter and the remainder, i.e., beyond the indenter-face sheet contact periphery to the outer dent edge. Based on these considerations, the total work done is evaluated as

$$V = Pw_o - \pi p_{oc} b^2 w_o - 2\pi p_{oc} \int_b^a w r dr \quad (5)$$

Substituting Equations (3) – (5) in Eq. (2) yields the total potential energy. The resultant expression is then minimized with respect to the maximum bending deflection, w_o , the dent radius, a , and the planar delamination radius, c , according to Equation (6).

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial w_o} = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial a} = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial c} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) produces three simultaneous non-linear equations that are solved numerically. In the present work, MATLAB's built-in function *lsqnonlin*, along with its default trust-region-reflective algorithm, was used [26]. The solutions were obtained in load increments of 1 N. It is worth noting that it was attempted to treat the problem as a more general multidimensional constrained optimization task. However, solutions with imaginary parts arose. As such, *lsqnonlin* was chosen to avoid manual filtering of unreasonable solutions. Termination tolerances were made more stringent than the default values to improve the solution accuracy. The simultaneous equations, as a result of Equation (6), for each successive load used for their initial values the solutions obtained from the preceding load. Understandably, the initial guess for the solution corresponding to the starting load played a significant role in determining the solution trajectories of w_o , a and c . Thus, the predicted value obtained at the end of *Regime I* for w_o and guessed values of a and c were used as the initial values for the starting load of *Regime II*. Because of existence of multiple local minimum values, constraints were used to obtain solutions that made physical sense. Firstly, a constraint was set so that the a and c solutions for the current load step were always greater than or equal to that of the preceding load step. Secondly, the slopes dP/da and dP/dc for the current load were also constrained to be greater than or equal to that of the preceding load. That is, for every load, the lower threshold values for these slopes were the slopes of the solutions obtained for the preceding load. Due to multiple solutions existing very close to each other, and the assumption that the planar delamination and dent radius grew as the load increased, it was critical to constrain the dP/da and dP/dc slopes with an upper critical threshold value which should not be exceeded. This was necessary as early solution trials showed that leaving this unconstrained resulted in the slopes suddenly jumping to infinity after a certain load, i.e. the trajectory of P vs. a and P vs. c suddenly became vertical.

2.3 Regime III: Unloading Regime

Predictions within the unloading regime follow the same procedure as that used in [18], where face sheet properties are homogenized at the peak load. However, in [18] this was based on an assumed c/a ratio, whereas in the current model values of c and a are used that were solved for at the peak load at the end of Regime II.

Representing any of the face sheet properties (D , E or ν) with the homogenized property Z^* , the value of Z^* in the present model is evaluated as

$$Z^* = \frac{c^2}{a^2} Z_{res} + \left(1 - \frac{c^2}{a^2}\right) Z_r \quad (7)$$

where, as previously, the subscripts “*res*” and “*r*” refer to the damaged and intact states, respectively. The Ritz method is then employed with these homogenized face sheet properties, which are constant over r . The bending and membrane energy equations for the unloading regime therefore become

$$U_b = \pi D^* \int_b^c \left[r \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2 + 2\nu^* \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} \right) \right] dr \quad (8)$$

$$U_m = \frac{\pi h_f}{4} \frac{E^*}{(1 - \nu^*)} \int_b^c r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^4 dr \quad (9)$$

where D^* , E^* and ν^* represent the homogenized properties of D , E and ν , respectively.

In the change from the loading to the unloading regime, the core is assumed to resist face sheet deflection by pulling against it with a constant core restoring pressure, p_{ot} . The core restoring pressure

in the unloading regime acts in the opposite direction to the core resistive pressure in the loading regime [18]. This modifies the total work formula for the unloading regime to

$$V = Pw_o + \pi p_{ot} b^2 w_o + 2\pi p_{ot} \int_b^a w(r) r dr \quad (10)$$

The total potential energy is calculated using Eqs (2) and (8) – (10). The evaluated total potential energy is minimized with respect to center displacement as

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial w_o} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) is first solved with a being the unknown and P and w_o known as obtained from the end of Regime II. This solution obtained for a from Eq. (11), called a_i , is a fraction of the maximum value of a (referred to henceforth as a_{max}) which was solved at the peak load at the end of Regime II. As discussed in Singh et al. [18], a_i represents the size of the circular region over which core “unwrinkling” initially occurs as soon as the load starts decreasing in the unloading regime. After solving for a_i , Eq. (11) is used to solve for w_o for the entire unloading regime. In this part of the solution process it is assumed that a increases linearly from a_i to a_{max} as P decreases from peak load to zero load. Physically, this means that unloading of the core occurs from the interior outwards. As a result, the dent radius at $P = 0$ is the same as a_{max} . Also, the permanent (or residual) dent depth corresponds to the value of w_o obtained when $P = 0$ and $a = a_{max}$. No numerical constraints were applied on any parameters during the unloading phase.

4 MODEL VALIDATION

The model was validated using experimental results obtained from Singh et al. [1, 27] for sandwich panels that utilized 8 ply IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy face sheets and 5052 aluminum honeycomb core. The 8 ply face sheets had nominal thicknesses of 1.02 mm and a quasi-isotropic layup of [45/0/-45/90]. Spherical indentors of diameters 25.4 mm and 76.2 mm were used for QSI. Table 1 presents properties of the indentors and the intact and damaged face sheets that were used in the model validation.

Three different honeycomb cores were used in the experiments, allowing sandwich plates containing cores with two different densities and two different thicknesses to be tested. The core types are designated as C1 (nominal), C2 (thin) and C3 (dense). Table 2 presents the core properties. All properties other than density and thickness were determined experimentally [20, 28] based on the idealized honeycomb core behavior proposed by Minakuchi et al. [29].

The model’s prediction for load versus deflection were compared to “master plots” of experimental results [18, 29] as well as to predictions by the earlier model of Singh et al. [18]. Experimental master plots combine experimental results for different specimens of each sandwich configuration for a particular indenter size and thereby average out specimen-to-specimen variations. Details of the exact procedure and the algorithm used for the development of the master plots are provided in Ref. [27].

Property	Value
E_f (GPa)	11.7
E_i (GPa)	200
ν_f	0
ν_i	0.33
D_r (Nm)	5.43
D_{res} (Nm)	0.188
E_r (GPa)	55.2
E_{res} (GPa)	11.7
ν_r	0.334
ν_{res}	0.153

Table 1: Face sheet and indenter properties.

Property	C1 Core	C2 Core	C3 Core
Core density, kg.m ³	49.7	49.7	72.1
Core thickness, mm	25.4	16.5	25.4
Transverse Compressive Modulus (E_{zc}), GPa	1.3	1.0	1.9
Transverse Tensile Modulus (E_{zt}), GPa	1.4	1.3	1.7
Crush Strength, (p_{cr}), MPa	2.2	2.6	5.0
Compressive Yield Strength (p_{oc}), MPa	0.96	1.1	1.8
Tensile Yield Strength (p_{ot}), MPa	0.44	0.49	0.94

Table 2: Honeycomb core properties.

5 RESULTS

Figures 4 – 7 present load versus displacement results for the four configurations studied. Figures 4 and 7 are for sandwich plates with the nominal C1 core indented with small and large indentors, respectively. Figures 5 and 6 are both for the QSI via the 25.4 mm diameter indenter, and present results for sandwich plates with the thinner C2 and denser C3 core, respectively. All figures present the experimental master plot along with predictions by both the two-region plate model and the model by Singh et al. [18]. It is pointed out that for the C3 core the peak load was higher than those for C1 and C2 cores. Due to a higher core density of the C3 core resulting in a stiffer core response, a higher load was needed to create damage that was barely visible [1]. One advantage of the current model is that it directly evaluates the percentage of the indented region that is damaged, and therefore the ratio of the delamination to dent radius, whereas in [18] this was assumed a priori. Just as in Ref. [18], an equivalent flat-nosed indenter assumption is used. This assumption, coupled with the low stiffness of the inner, damaged region, causes the face sheet deformations to be relatively localized which restricts the current model to relatively thin face sheets. The two-region plate model captures the overall mechanistic behavior of the sandwich response better than the model by Singh et al. [18]. This is true for all the indenter sizes and core types considered and is obvious from the slightly more stiffened response the two-region plate model exhibits at higher loads in figures 4-7. The response is similar to what was observed experimentally.

Figure 4: Load versus displacement plots of 8 ply face sheet sandwich structures with C1 core indented with 25.4 mm diameter indenter.

Figure 5: Load versus displacement plots of 8 ply sandwich structure with thinner (C2) core indented with 25.4 mm diameter indenter.

Figure 6: Load versus displacement plots of 8 ply face sheet sandwich structures with denser (C3) core indented with 25.4 mm diameter indenter.

Figure 7: Load versus displacement plots of 8 ply face sheet sandwich structures with C1 core indented with 76.2 mm diameter indenter.

Table 3 presents a summary of experimental and model predicted peak displacement and residual dent depths for the cases represented by figures 4-7. The peak displacements in Table 3 were determined from the master plots that were created using experimental data for each sandwich configuration. As seen from the numbers presented in Table 3, the model predicts with reasonable accuracy the peak displacement and residual dent depths. Even though these predictions were also reasonably accurate in the model by Singh et al. [18], the earlier stated advantages of the two-region plate model clearly scores it as an improved model from that of Singh et al. [18].

Core Type	Indenter Size, mm	Peak Displacement, mm		Residual Dent Depth, mm	
		Model	Experimental	Model	Experimental
C1	25.4	1.32	1.34	0.55	0.50
C2	25.4	1.26	1.32	0.53	0.47
C3	25.4	1.33	1.34	0.44	0.53
C1	76.2	2.40	2.49	1.20	1.04

Table 3: Predicted and experimentally determined peak and residual displacements.

Table 4 presents the summary of predicted and experimentally determined dent radius (a) and planar delamination radius (c) results for all sandwich configurations considered for model validation. As stated earlier, experimental dent radius was determined by taking the average dent radius of sandwich configurations of the same type indented with the same indenter size to a similar load. The experimental planar delamination radius was determined by first measuring the planar delamination area using the procedure described in Ref. [1]. This made use of inbuilt features in the C-scan data analysis software where a boundary around the overall 2D delamination periphery was created and the software computed the area enclosed by the boundary. The planar delamination radius was then calculated assuming an “equivalent” circular area to that computed by the C-scan data analysis software. No experimental planar delamination radius data was available for the 76.2 mm indentation case. As explained in Ref. [27], the planar delamination boundaries were not clearly defined for this case and therefore no radius value was evaluated.

Table 4 shows that, overall, the model predicts dent radius with reasonable accuracy. For planar delamination radius, the prediction is better for the stiffer (C2 and C3) cores than the nominal (C1) core. Note from the results presented in Table 4 that the planar delamination radius is less than the dent radius for every case considered. This agrees with what has been observed experimentally [1].

Core Type	Indenter Size, mm	Dent Radius, mm		Planar Delamination Radius, mm	
		Model	Experimental	Model	Experimental
C1	25.4	23.4	18.4	15.1	7.9
C2	25.4	22.2	17.0	14.7	9.8
C3	25.4	17.8	16.0	11.9	10.6
C1	76.2	33.3	29.0	19.9	Not Available

Table 4: Predicted and experimentally determined dent and planar delamination radius.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The two-region plate model developed in this research is able to predict the loading and unloading response, as well as the residual dent diameter, dent depth and planar radius of delamination of thin face sheet composite sandwich structures undergoing quasi-static indentation loading. The model considered damage created using small and large spherical indentors and is valid up to the barely visible external damage threshold. The initial low load elastic regime utilizes fundamental engineering mechanics based approach for deformation of an isotropic plate on an elastic foundation. From the onset of face sheet and core damage, which are assumed to occur simultaneously, the model employs a two-region plate model based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method of energy minimization. The primary utility of the model is predicting residual dent depths, dent diameters and planar delamination radius is done with reasonable accuracy for thin face sheet sandwich structures. The overall mechanistic behavior of the sandwich response is captured more correctly than what was achieved in the previous model by Singh et al. [18]. In its current form the model may prove to be useful in a variety of ways, including for parametric trade-off studies, for damage tolerance and damage assessments, and to develop input for other damage tolerance models, especially implementing a pre-existing damage state into a compression-after-impact model.

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